

Product/Market Growth Strategies and Challenges of an Organic Product Trader in Northern Luzon

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ABSTRACT

This study was undertaken to determine the market-product growth strategies and challenges of an organic trader in Northern Luzon in the areas of market penetration, product development, market development, and diversification. Qualitative case study method of analysis was used to evaluate the profile, market-product growth strategies, and challenges encountered along the growth strategies of the agricultural organic product trader. Documents on certifications and product lines were collected and the establishment's manager was the study's key informant. Findings revealed that the cooperative federation has been operating for 11 years now, has been accredited by the Organic Certification Center of the Philippines (OCCP) Inspection and Certification Services, Inc., and offers OCCP-certified fruits and vegetables, non-certified crops and processing plants including rice milling, postharvest facility for fruits and vegetables, drying, storage and selling area. The cooperative federation caters to customers who physically visit and buy from their store and customers from the Department of Education Division of Nueva Vizcaya who buys their veggie chips and banana chips per week. Government and non-government organizations provide technical and financial support. The market-product growth strategies are applied by the cooperative federation but there are still areas for improvement to assist them to improve their strategies. Lack of customer service and marketing strategies training, better food processing techniques, unattractive packaging and labeling of products, and limited supply of raw materials to meet the production quota were identified as challenges on market-product growth strategies. Possible interventions were identified to help the cooperative grow its market and product through an extension program.

Keywords: market penetration, product development, market development, diversification

INTRODUCTION

Beyond reviewing current companies, according to Kotler and Armstrong (2016), planning a business portfolio entails identifying businesses and products that the organization should consider in the future. If companies want to compete more efficiently and satisfy their stakeholders, they need to expand. The aim of the organization must be to manage "profitable growth." The primary responsibility for achieving sustainable growth for the business rests with marketing. Marketers must recognize, analyze, and select business opportunities, as well as develop strategies to capture them. The Ansoff product/market expansion grid is a valuable method for finding growth opportunities.

Kotler and Armstrong (2016) stated that the Product/Market Expansion Grid is a portfolio-planning method for defining company growth opportunities such as market penetration, market development, product development, and diversification. Market penetration is a company growth strategy by increasing sales of current products to current market segments without changing the product while market development is a company growth by identifying and developing new market segments for current company products. Product development refers to offering modified or new products to current market segment while diversification means starting up or acquiring businesses outside the company's current products and markets (Kotler and Armstrong, 2016). It may be related or unrelated diversification. Related diversification refers to adding new but related products or services while unrelated diversification is adding new, unrelated products or services (Fred, 2011).

Market development is one of the program components of the Philippines' National Organic Agriculture Program (NOAP). The Departments of Agriculture and Trade and Industry partnered to create an annual program to encourage organic agriculture at local and international trade shows, through local and international trade fairs, market promotion and matching activities with active participation from multi-stakeholder groups/organizations, advocates and networks to push for organic products in the local and international markets. Furthermore, in supermarket establishments, they designate an area where organic goods, as well as IEC materials and collaterals attesting to the benefits of eating organic foods, are prominently displayed. Despite the government's support activities for traders, these traders still face difficulties in marketing their organic products because they cater to a niche market (health-conscious customers) and have a price premium of 20 to 30 percent (Maghirang, de la Cruz, and Villareal, 2011).

There are only four (4) organic product traders in the province of Nueva Vizcaya, which is part of the Cagayan Valley Region (Region 02), according to the Office of Provincial Agriculture. These traders' target markets include health-conscious consumers, food establishments, patients/senior citizens who have been referred by physicians, and individual customers from Manila who attend trade shows. The number of customers they have per day, however, is still limited.

The researchers chose Agrizkaya Cooperative Federation as the focus of their study because it is the only organization that has been operating continuously throughout the pandemic. They've also been processing fruits and vegetables with the assistance of the Department of Science and Technology (DOST). Their cause is organic agriculture. They produce, process, and market organic agricultural inputs and products.

In terms of their product lines for organic fruits and vegetables at this time of pandemic, they only sell lettuce due to typhoons that hit their organic farms last year. They also process fruits and vegetables purchased from certified Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs). Furthermore, they also sell processed products of these SMEs. These products are only distributed in the local setting where such sector is not stable or not growing, thus there is a need to come up with market-product growth strategies.

In the study conducted by Adalem, Garra, Palina, & Villanueva (2019) on marketing challenges of organic traders, they found out that additional costs are incurred when the product is not in its proper condition, when products come in varying sizes, when defective & unsold products are replaced, and loss of the usual quality. In addition other challenges that contribute to additional costs include selling the organic vegetables at lower prices, limited production and lack of manpower which leads to refusal of contracts, limited opportunities for participation in the trade fairs conducted by the Department of Agriculture, print or non-print media that do not serve its purposes, and limited expertise or competence in coming up with marketing paraphernalia.

With the preceding information and data discussed, this study aimed to determine the organic trader product/market growth strategies and challenges. These will be used as a starting point for creating a growth strategy intervention based on the study's findings to help them broaden their products and markets through an extension program.

The findings of the study will benefit the following: (a) Traders of organic agricultural products in the province of Nueva Vizcaya. Results of the study shall benefit them inasmuch as this study will provide a better understanding about challenges affecting them in their market-product growth strategies and will provide a framework that they can use to address these challenges. With this intervention, it is expected that their markets and products will increase; (b) Concerned government agencies like DA and DTI. Results of the study shall make them informed about the current status of the trader in terms of their market-product growth strategies, and thus, craft supportive policies that further expand their markets and products; (c) SMU School of Accountancy and Business. The results of the study will serve as a learning material in subjects such as Entrepreneurship, Business Policies and Strategies and Marketing. Business students who are made to understand the unique challenges affecting the growth of organic products traders may gain insights on what strategies to implement in such a situation. The outcome of this study can also serve as a reference for developing possible activities to support the advocacy and promotion of consuming organic agricultural products; (d) The Researchers. This study will serve as a springboard to better understand the growth organic agricultural markets and products. This will further enhance the researchers' knowledge on marketing organic agricultural products and will help them develop learning materials for a more empirical-based lectures and classroom activities; (e) Future researchers. The framework and tool used in this study will serve as guide for future researches focusing on marketing organic agricultural products considering other variables and models.

The Ansoff Matrix, also called the Product/Market Expansion Grid, is a tool used by firms to analyze and plan their strategies for growth. The matrix shows four strategies that can be used to help a firm grow and also analyzes the risk associated with each strategy (google.com).

In this study, the researchers identified the existing growth strategies and challenges encountered by the organic product trader and recommended possible extension program interventions to assist the trader in growing its products and markets based on the results of the study.

Conceptual and Analytical Framework

The Ansoff Product/Market Grid

The following terms are defined for a better understanding of the study: (1) **Market penetration**, which is a company growth by increasing sales of current products to current market segments without changing the product (Kotler and Armstrong, 2016). In this study, it refers to how the organic product traders increase the sales of their current products to their existing customers; (2) **Market development**, refers to company growth by identifying and developing new market segments for current company products (Kotler and Armstrong, 2016). In this study, it refers to how the organic product traders create/find new customers for their existing products; (3) **Product development**, is a company growth by offering modified or new products to current market segment (Kotler and Armstrong, 2016). As used in the study, it refers to the new products being offered by the organic product traders to their existing customers; and 4) **Diversification which involves** starting up or acquiring businesses outside the company's current products and markets (Kotler and Armstrong, 2016). In this research, it refers to the new products being offered by the organic product traders to their new customers.

This study aimed to determine and analyze the market-product growth strategies and challenges of an organic product trader in Northern Luzon. Specifically, it sought to carry out the following: (1) determine the profile of the organic product trader in terms of a) type of business ownership; (b) years of operation; (c) government organic certification; (d) product lines; (e) purchase volume; (f) sales volume per day; (g) kinds of markets/customers served; (h) number of customers per day; and (i) government support received; (2) determine and analyze the product and market growth strategies of the organic product trader along the areas of (a) market penetration; (b) product development; (c) market development; and (d) diversification; (3) identify the challenges encountered by the organic product trader in its existing product and market growth strategies along the above-stated areas; and (4) recommend possible interventions to assist the organic product trader expand its products and markets through an extension program.

METHODOLOGY

Using Ansoff's Product/Market Expansion Grid (Kotler and Armstrong, 2016), the study used the qualitative case study method of analysis to evaluate the profile, market-product growth strategies, and challenges encountered along the growth strategies of the agricultural organic product

trader. The establishment's manager was the study's key informant. To back up the information from the interview, documents on certifications and product lines were collected.

The data were gathered through personal interviews *with* the manager of the cooperative federation. Specifically, first, a permission was asked from the manager of the organic trading; second, interview was scheduled with the organic trading manager along the product/ market growth strategies in terms of market penetration, market development, product development, and diversification as well the challenges encountered. Documents were requested and scanned to validate the responses; lastly, the interview responses were transcribed followed by the analyses of the transcribed data.

The study was conducted with adherence to strict data confidentiality and compliance to seeking respondents' permission and informed consent.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Section 1. The Organic Product Trader's Profile

The Agrizkaya Cooperative Foundation is a cooperative federation. The company has been in operation for 11 years. The Organic Certification Center of the Philippines (OCCP) Inspection and Certification Services, Inc. accredited the company in 2018. It is a third-party accrediting agency for organic products in the Philippines. OCCP-certified fruits, vegetables, and grain crops are available through the cooperative. Perennials (fruits), leafy plants, legume crops, and root crops are also being offered by the cooperative. Ice cream, squash powder, turmeric tea, banana wine, squash polvoron, rice wine, rattan fruit, vinegar with chili, banana chips, *gabi* (taro), *sitao* (string beans), and *siling sinigang* (green chili pepper) are among their non-certified crops. Rice milling, a postharvest plant for fruits and vegetables, drying, storage, and a sale area are all part of the cooperative's processing facilities. Since almost all of the items are seasonal, the cooperative's amount of transactions for fresh fruits and vegetables is dictated by product availability. The cooperative extended its activities to include the manufacture of vegetable chips, banana chips, turmeric teas, ice creams, and durian candies. Based on the observations of Agrizkaya's manager, Mrs. Eden Lacar, when prices are high, farmers deliver more goods. Before the pandemic, the cooperative bought 200-300 kilos of vegetables per harvest on average for *'pinakbet'*, a popular vegetable dish in the northern part of the country. The cooperative buys 35 kilos of vegetables per commodity per week on average for *'chopsuey'*, another popular vegetable dish in the Philippines. Purchases of these vegetables however decline when supply falls off during the off-season. They don't have any certified organic vegetables right now because they were hit by typhoons in the fourth quarter of the year 2020. They do, however, purchase root crops for processing from their certified SMEs.

The organic products delivered by farmers to the cooperative are sold in various outlets like the cooperative's store, Dizon Farms located at NVAT, trade fairs organized by the Department of Trade and Industry. These are also directly sold to employees and patients of NVPH as recommended by their doctors and to restaurants in Cauayan City, Manila and Baguio City. When the cooperative's staff travel to other locations for conferences or trainings, they bring organic items with them to sell to the other attendees. When asked how many customers come to their store on a daily or weekly basis, Mrs. Lacar said that there are days when only a few people come in but there are also occasions when a lot of people come in. Other staff members assist when an influx of customers happens. Except for the Department of Education Division of Nueva Vizcaya (which has 165 elementary schools) which buys their veggie chips and banana chips once a week, they have an average of 10 customers per day (old and new) who purchase from them.

Government organizations are often asked to help the cooperative develop their services to the community. For instance, the cooperative training on organic production and marketing, packaging, and labeling was provided by the Department of Trade and Industry (DTI). The Department of Science and Technology (DOST) offered training and technical assistance to the cooperative in the preparation of ice cream from *guyabano* (soursop), *ube* (purple yam), and mango. The Department of Agriculture-Region 02 on the other hand issued 1,000 pieces of packaging and labeling materials to the cooperative, as well as P519,000 in financial assistance for organic certification with the Organic Certification Center of the Philippines over a three-year period (P173,000 per year). The Cagayan Valley Research Center (CVRC) provided training and technology on food processing, organic farming and crop production. Through Fr. Gerry Bouckaert, CICM, it obtained a P3,000,000 grant from West Flanders, Belgium. In addition, Primary Cooperatives' share capital has been invested with them. Trainings, building rentals, stall rentals, and office rentals are some of the cooperative's sources of funds for its various operations. The cooperative buys and sells agricultural inputs, conducts trainings/seminars for cooperatives, and processes organic agricultural products to raise revenue from the above funds.

On May 21, 2015, Department of Agriculture (DA) Secretary Proceso Alcala inaugurated the Cagayan Valley Regional Organic Trading Center (ROTC) in Bagabag, Nueva Vizcaya. According to Alcala, the author who wrote RA 10068, the Organic Agriculture Act of 2010, the center will be a model for holistic and sustainable agricultural development through organic farming. The 183-hectare Nueva Vizcaya Experiment Station has been transformed into the Philippines' first organic trading center, which is now open to farmers, traders, and buyers. An agribusiness development center, an organic native chicken production center, an administration building, a fruit processing and packaging building, a wild pig conservation and production center, and a GAP vegetable production center are among the facilities at the center (<https://organic-market.info/news-in-brief-and-reports-article/philippines-first-organic-trading-center-now-open.html>).

Section 2. Product/Market Growth Strategies

A. Market Penetration

Market penetration refers to the company growth achieved by increasing sales of current products to current market segments without changing the product (Kotler and Armstrong, 2016). The participation of general retailers in the organic food industry, which reduces costs and thereby increases the customer base, is critical to the market share for organic goods. (Maghirang, de la Cruz, and Villareal, 2011).

The following are the market penetration strategies of the organic product trader:

1. Availability of Products in the main store and in Metro Manila

At this time, the Agrizkaya Cooperative Federation has two marketing staff serving walk-in customers. Their main store in Almaguer North, Bambang, Nueva Vizcaya, sells their own organic fruits and vegetables, both fresh and processed. They also sell agricultural inputs like fertilizers and seeds, as well as processed foods from small businesses, while the San Dionisio Store in Manila only sells turmeric teas.

2. Online and offline promotion

Their Facebook page, "Agrizkaya Organics," as well as their store signage, are used to advertise their products. They use their Facebook account to advertise their products in order to boost sales. They also offer discounts for bulk orders, such as 10% off for every 5 bottles of turmeric tea purchased and 5% off for a 25-kg bag of rice.

3. Participation in Trade Fairs

They attended the DTI and DOST trade shows held at Robinson's Mall in Tuguegarao City last year. But, prior to the pandemic, they had been attending DOST and DTI trade fairs in Tuguegarao City and Manila every year for three (3) years.

The goal of market penetration is to increase revenue, specifically the amount of sales. The following methods can be used to achieve this goal: increasing market share; increasing the amount of sales of products; increasing the volume of purchases of goods by the consumer; and providing new ways for consumers to use the commodity. When choosing a penetration strategy, the company's revenue and profits are saved or increased by maintaining and/or raising the company's market share. Since the business operates in a well-known and familiar market and deals with a well-known product, the risks are small (V V Kukartsev et al ,2019). In our research, the trader increases its market share by selling its products in its stores, using signage and facebook page, and participating in trade fairs.

B. Market Development

In market development, the company grows by identifying and developing new market segments for current company products (Kotler and Armstrong, 2016). The market development strategies of the trader are as follows:

1. Expansion of Market in Metro Manila

DILG and DOH employees in Manila are the cooperative federation's only new customers. These clients buy rice and turmeric teas from the cooperative. They deliver their customers' orders through the Nueva Vizcaya Agricultural Terminal's delivery truck (NVAT) until

Balintawak, Metro Manila (shipping point). Transportation costs 3.00 pesos per kilo. In general, Manila is a good potential market expansion for organic temperate upland vegetables, especially when sold in Malls or Supermarkets, since people frequent these locations for shopping. Organic products are sold at supermarket outlets of Rustan's, SM, Landmark, Shopwise, and others (Maghirang, de la Cruz, and Villareal, 2011). This is supported by the study of De Kleijn, Borgstein, de Jager, Hack, & Zimmermann (1995) in which they created a marketing plan for the sector based on the findings in order to expand the organic market in the Netherlands. This approach aims to expand the industry by first developing the market and then penetrating the market. According to them, this can be achieved by lowering production prices, improving organics' appearance, and making fresh organic produce available all year.

According to V V Kukartsev et al (2019), market development is best suited to businesses with marketing expertise, such as those with experience and resources for creating successful promotional campaigns, working with clients, and identifying distribution channels. This strategy's aim is to adapt and promote the company's existing goods for new markets. Implementation tools for the strategy include the use of alternative distribution platforms, the search for and seize of new consumer segments, and the discovery of sales prospects in new geographic regions. The risk of releasing an existing product in a new market after it has already been modified is much higher, and the costs are higher. However, there is the possibility of increased revenue.

One of the key components or programs of the National Organic Agriculture Program (NOAP) is Market Development. Section 5 of the relevant provisions states that "There is hereby established a comprehensive organic agricultural program through the promotion and commercialization of organic farming practices, cultivation and adoption and processing methods which have already been developed or to be developed, continuing research and upgrading thereof, the capacity building of farmers and the education of consumers thereon, the extension of assistance to local government units (LGUs), people's organizations (POs), non-government organizations (NGOs) and other stakeholders including individuals and groups who are willing to do other pertinent activities, and documentation and evaluation of the program. However, the trader still needs the assistance of other organizations in seizing market opportunities.

C. Product Development

Product development is a company strategy growth by offering modified or new products to current market segment (Kotler and Armstrong, 2016). In terms of product development strategy, the trader processes fruits and vegetables for its current markets.

1. Introduction of processed fruits and vegetables

Different flavors of ice cream, such as guyabano (sour sop) ice cream, ube (purple yam) ice cream, and durian ice cream, are among the new products sold by the cooperative to their current customers. They also sell durian candies and turmeric teas in a number of flavors. In the study of Perry, C. (1987), the terms that describe growth strategies are defined, and principles for selecting among them are established. It is known that growth strategies should be niche strategies, and it is hypothesized that business development and product development strategies are the most effective strategies.

In the study of V V Kukartsev et al (2019), product development strategy or product extension is best suited to technology and technology-related businesses. The aim is to provide an improved product to the consumer (current customers) with fresh, more appealing, and new features. Product range expansion; development of a new product generation (models); modernization of existing products by adding new properties and functions or enhancing their quality; product range expansion; creation of a new product generation (models); creation and introduction of a completely new product are among the product growth tools. As a result, this is much more expensive, but as experience has shown, offering a new (updated) product to existing markets is a much less risky approach. Agrizkaya Cooperative Federation also uses product development as a tool to expand its product line by processing organic fruits and vegetables.

D. Diversification

Diversification is practiced when the company grows through starting up or acquiring businesses outside the company's current products and markets (Kotler and Armstrong, 2016).

For the cooperative's diversification strategies, they recently diversified into processing food-related products and offer these to their new customers.

1. Expansion of product lines from organic fruits, vegetables and grains to processed food products

The vegetable chips (a combination of dehydrated squash, string beans (sitao), malunggay (moringa) leaves, carrots, and potatoes) and banana chips are the new products they sell to their new markets. The Department of Education, Division of Nueva Vizcaya (with 165 elementary schools) is the primary target market for these products, with 6 servings per week catering to 73,866 pupils/students. The contract with the Department of Education took effect in December 2020, but product development and delivery only began in January 2021. Oladimeji, M. S. & Udosen, I. (2019) in their study revealed that in terms of Return on Asset (ROA) and Return on Investment (ROI), diversified organizations outperform undiversified ones. They found out that diversified related companies have a positive return on investment (ROI) of 26.8%. A diversification strategy contributes to growth and profitability (20%). According to their study's findings, diversification is a strategic strategy for achieving strategic relevance and spontaneous performance.

In the research conducted by V V Kukartsev et al (2019), diversification is the most difficult and dangerous strategy, but it also has the greatest potential for success. Companies may be encouraged to diversify naturally for a variety of reasons, including: this approach appears to be profitable; the current business model has run its course; a new path does not necessitate major or risky investments; diversification would allow for greater financial stability due to the distribution of risks across different product lines, industries, and other factors. The aim is to introduce new products to previously untapped markets. There are two types of diversification. The first is horizontal diversification: a new direction of the company's operation does not vary significantly from the current ones, but rather complements them. The second is vertical diversification: a new direction of the company's activity differs radically from the existing ones, but rather complements them. In its most basic form, diversification strategy entails developing and releasing new goods while expanding into new markets. In this strategy, the costs and risks are very high. In our study, the Agrizkaya Cooperative Federation has diversified into horizontal/ related diversification because it processes fresh organic produce into food products and plans to extend its product line.

Section 3. Challenges in Product/Market Growth Strategies

1. Market Penetration Challenges

- 1.1 Lack of distributors/ stores. Only their main store at Almaguer North, Bambang, Nueva Vizcaya and the San Dionisio store in Manila are their distributors.

- 1.2 Facebook page is not updated. The Facebook account is not always updated because the cooperative lacks marketing staff to update the page. In addition, Mrs. Lacar claims that they are unable to distribute flyers and brochures at this time because these materials are still being improved or refined. They need the assistance of an IT specialist, but due to a lack of funds, they are unable to employ additional personnel. Since the cooperative lacks a marketing officer, the cooperative's other employees are the ones promoting their products in order to boost sales.

2. Product Development Challenges

- 2.1 lack of space/building for production area. The production area is limited to accommodate the machines, tools, and equipment to manufacture the product

- 2.2 lack of equipment (e.g. mixer). A mixer is needed by the cooperative in order to facilitate the processing of the products.

3. Market Development Challenges

- 3.1 lack of distribution channels. The cooperative lacks distribution outlets for their products, such as distributors/retailers or stores.

- 3.2 lack of marketing staff. The problem they face in market growth is the lack of marketing personnel who can identify new market segments for their existing products.

4. Diversification Challenges

4.1 inefficient packing– The manual packing of the vegetable chips and banana chips takes a long time.

4.2 not attractive labeling. Labeling for the vegetable chips and banana chips is not really appealing. Also, the information on the label is unreadable.

4.3 limited supply of raw materials (fruits and vegetables) to meet the production quotas. The supply of fruits and vegetables is limited because many were destroyed by the typhoons in the last quarter of the previous year.

4.4 limited number of production workers. They lack manufacturing staff to handle the goods' sorting, packaging, and labeling.

4.5 lack of better food processing techniques. They need improved food manufacturing techniques to achieve the desired finished product texture

4.6. lack of facilities for diversification. They also want to experiment with making blue ternate jam (made from an anti-cancer plant) and biscuits and cakes out of squash and carrots. However, they lack the required facilities (for example, a bakery) and equipment, as well as the necessary expertise to manufacture these products.

Product/ Market Growth Strategy Matrix of Agrizkaya Cooperative Federation Using the Ansoff Product/Market Expansion Grid

	CURRENT PRODUCTS	NEW PRODUCTS
CURRENT MARKETS	<p>MARKET PENETRATION Strategies</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Availability of Products in the main store and in Metro Manila 2. Online and offline promotion 3. Participation in Trade Fairs <p>Challenges: lack of distributors/stores, Facebook page is not updated</p>	<p>PRODUCT DEVELOPMENT Strategies:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Introduction of processed fruits and vegetables <p>Challenges: lack of space/building for production area, lack of equipment (e.g. mixer)</p>
NEW MARKETS	<p>MARKET DEVELOPMENT Strategies</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Expansion of market in Metro Manila <p>Challenges: Lack of distribution channels, lack of marketing staff</p>	<p>DIVERSIFICATION Strategies</p> <p>Related Diversification</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Expansion of product lines from organic vegetables and grains to processed fruits <p>Challenges: inefficient packing, not attractive labeling, lack of supply of raw materials, (vegetables), lack of production workers, lack of better food processing techniques, limited facilities for diversification.</p>

Section 3. Extension Program Interventions to Assist the Cooperative Federation in Growing Its Products and Markets

Based on the salient findings in sections 1 and 2 of this study, the following interventions are deemed necessary: (1) Market Research. New Market Segments in both the local and national markets should be identified through market research; (2) Training on Labeling. To provide training on labeling so that labels are more attractive; (3) Information and communications technology assistance from ICT experts. The cooperative's Facebook page should be updated and products should be posted in the DOST One Store website with the help of the ICT experts; (4) Marketing assistance/training. To assist the cooperative in selling its products by deploying On-the-Job trainees and development of integrated marketing communication tools; and (5) Training /Assistance in new product development. To conduct training on new product development

Conclusions and Recommendations

Agrizkaya is a federation of cooperatives that produces and sells organic fresh and processed crops. Its operation was approved by the OCCP and the FDA. On average, daily number of customers is still limited. It receives trainings and other technical assistance from various government agencies. The cooperative's product/market growth strategies are still minimal and challenges in all the growth strategies are currently experienced. Identifying new consumer segments, improving labeling design, updating Facebook posts and posting products and articles on the DOST One Store website, and assistance in manufacturing and selling their products are all useful interventions to help the cooperative expand its market and products.

Based on the conclusions, this study recommends that the cooperative broadens its market by networking and forging partnerships with potential distributors. They must continue their participation in trade fairs organized by DOST, DTI, and DA and explore the possibility of joining trade fairs during the annual "Ammungan" festival. They should also intensify their advertising campaigns by utilizing not only the print media but also social media. The Academe should help the organic trader grow their markets and products by offering extension programs based from the results of the study and thoroughly discussed with the target beneficiary. The school may also consider sending their on-the-job trainees in business, accountancy or information technology to help with their operations.

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Interview Guide

1. **Profile**-To determine the profile of organic product traders in terms of
 - a. What is the type of ownership of your business?
 - b. How many years has your business been operating?

- c. What type of government organic certification does your business have?
- d. What product lines do you offer?
- e. How many kilograms of organic products do you buy per purchase per week?
- f. What kinds of markets/customers do you serve/have?
- g. How many customers per day do you have?
- h. How much is your sales per day per product?
- i. How many kilograms/units of each product are sold per day?
- j. What government support did you receive(funding, trainings)?

2. Product/ Market Growth Strategies

A. Market Penetration- Company growth by increasing sales of current products to current market segments without changing the product (Kotler and Armstrong, 2016). In this study, it refers to how the organic product traders increase the amount of sales of their current products to their current customers.

1. Do you have salespersons (salesladies and salesmen)? How many?
2. Do you have distribution networks/distributors? What/who are they?
3. What communication channels/media do you use to promote your products (brochures, flyers, facebook, website, radio, television, tarpaulin, signage, etc.? Do you upgrade/update these? How?
4. Do you offer promotions like discounts, free products?
5. Do you attend trade fairs? What are these? How often?
6. Do you extend/offer credit for bulk/large purchases? How much is the credit limit? How long is the credit period?
7. What other strategies do you implement in order to increase your sales?
8. What concerns or challenges have you encountered-on market penetration?

B. Market development - Company growth by identifying and developing new market segments for current company products(Kotler and Armstrong, 2016). In this research, it refers to how the organic product traders create/find new customers for their current products.

1. Do you have new customers here in the province? Who are they? How many are they?
2. Do you have customers in other provinces/cities? Where?
3. Who are your customers in these places? How many are they?
4. Do you have outlets/stores in other places? Where? How many?
5. What products do they buy from you?
6. How many kilograms of each product do they buy per day?
7. What concerns or challenges have you encountered on market development?

C. Product development - Company growth by offering modified or new products to current market segment(Kotler and Armstrong, 2016). As used in this study, it refers to the new products being offered by the organic product traders to their current customers.

1. What product improvement/innovation do you do to better respond to the needs of consumers?
2. What other products do you offer to attract new customers?
2. Do you offer different varieties of your products? What are these? How many?
3. Do you manufacture/process products? What are these?
4. What other products can be developed or purchased to support the unique selling proposition of your business organization?
5. What concerns or challenges have you encountered on product development?

D. Diversification- Company growth through starting up or acquiring businesses outside the company's current products and markets (Kotler and Armstrong, 2016). In this study, it refers to the new products being offered by the organic product traders to their new customers.

1. Do you offer new products/brands? What are these?
2. Who are the customers of these new products/brands?
3. Do you modify/change your products that can create a new market by introducing new uses for the product?
4. What are the new uses of these products?
5. How many farmers do you have? Where are they located?
6. What other businesses do you have?
7. What unrelated products do you offer?
8. What concerns or challenges have you encountered-on diversification?